

Comparative evaluation of pain perception following use of clove gel, sweetening agent ,cryotherapy, lignocaine gel before local anesthesia administration in 6–12 yrs old children: a randomized control study

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Abstract

Primary reason for children seeking a dental care in the developing world is pain. A number of methods have been suggested to reduce the pain induced by penetration of local anesthetic agents. These include application of topical anesthetics, suggestion, distraction techniques, alteration of factors related to injection solutions such as pH and temperature and a reduced speed of injection. The aim of this study is to assess the efficacy of cryotherapy applications on the success of an inferior alveolar nerve block (IANB) to reduce pain severity during a pulpectomy of primary molars. A randomized parallel controlled trial includes 170 healthy children aged 4 to 10 years who complained of carious primary mandibular molars. After an IANB administration, ice packs (cryotherapy group) is applied to half of the participants while the other half did not receive ice packs. During extraction and pulpectomy, pain severity is tested using the Wong Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale

(WBS). Children's behavior was assessed using Frankl's Behavior Rating Scale (FBRS) before and after clinical procedures.

Introduction

Primary reason for children seeking a dental care is pain. Needle phobia is the most common dental fear among children. A number of methods have been suggested to reduce the pain induced by penetration of local anesthetic agents. These include application of topical anesthetics, suggestion, distraction techniques, alteration of factors related to injection solutions such as pH and temperature and a reduced speed of injection. In the field of dentistry, topical anesthesia plays an important role in reducing pain during needle pricks. Topical anesthesia agents are the gold standard methods among the various methods to relieve pain. Benzocaine and lignocaine gel are most commonly used gel for topical anesthesia. Application of ice before and after painful procedures have been practiced for years. The use of plant extract and their incorporation in the dental material for various purposes has shown promising results. Sweet taste sensations before dental injections in children help to control the associated pain. This effect is influenced by the individual's sweet taste tendency.¹ The purpose of this study was to compare and evaluate pain perception following topical application of lignocaine gel, clove gel, sweetening agent and cryotherapy during intraoral injection in children.¹

Materials and Methods

Parents of the patients were explained about the study, an informed consent was taken in the language they understood. Ethical clearance was taken from the ethical committee of the institute. Forty children in the age group 6 to 12 years who required local anesthesia administration for dental treatment (pulp therapy, extractions) were included in this study. Uncooperative patients were excluded from this study. Children were randomly allocated to four different groups: Group I (Clove gel), Group II (sweetening agent), Group III (cryotherapy) and Group IV (Lignocaine gel) (10 in each group). Prior to administration of local anesthesia, in Group I, clove gel was applied using a cotton swab and held in for a duration of 2 minutes.² In Group II, the subjects were asked to hold 10 mL of Glucose solution in their mouth for 2 min.¹

Fig. 1 (colgate Painout clove gel)

Fig.2 (holding sweetening solution)

In Group III, cryotherapy (ice pretreatment) was given on the injection site for 2 min. The ice tube was prepared from the small finger portion of latex gloves.³

In Group IV Lignocaine gel was applied using a cotton swab.²

Fig. 3 (ice tube with latex gloves)

Fig.4 (topical lignocaine gel)

After application of topical agents in all respective groups, local anesthesia administration was done and pain perception score was assessed. Behaviour of children was assessed using Wong Baker pain scale and SEM criteria.⁴

Groups (WBPS)	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV	ately painful	4.Painful
Mean±SD	2.60±1.90	2.00±1.33	0.80±1.03	3.40±1.90	Verbal complaints, e.g., "ow", moans	Verbal complaints indicating intense pain
Eyes	no eye signs of discomfort		Eyes wide, showing concern, but no tears	watery eyes and/ or flinching eyes		Crying tears running down the face
Motars	Hands relaxed;no apparent body tenseness		Hands show some distress or tension, grasping chair due to discomfort, muscular tension	Random movements of arms or body without aggressive intention to make physical contact, grimace, twitch		Movement of hands trying to make aggressive physical contact

Table 1. SEM scale (Sound, Eye, Motor Scale).

Fig.5. Wong baker Pain Scale

Result

The data are tabulated in Microsoft excel and analysed with SPSS V.24 software. Chi square test and One way ANOVA are used for the statistical analysis. The p value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. There was statistically significant difference between group in by using wong Baker Pain scale which was 0.006.(table. 2) There was statistically significant difference between group in by using SEM Scale which was 0.007.(table. 3). The mean score was highest in Group 4 followed by Group 1, Group 2 and lowest in Group 3.(fig.6 and fig.7)

P value	0.006
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Table .2

Groups (SEM)	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
Mean±SD	2.30±0.95	2.00±0.67	1.40±0.52	2.70±0.95
P value	0.007			

Table.3

Fig.6 Comparison of pain perception score(WBS)

Fig.7 Comparison of pain perception score(SEM)

Discussion

Needle phobias , most precisely fear of pain due to needle prick is most frequently encountered in a child. Various methods have been developed to overcome this problem. Topical anesthesia agents are the most common and easily available.⁵This study was conducted to compare and evaluate pain perception following topical application of lignocaine gel, clove gel, sweetening agent and cryotherapy before administration of local anesthesia in children. In the current study age group of 6 and above were selected because of improved cognitive ability.⁵The WBFRS was used because it is simple and used easily in younger age group. The SEM

scale was used as it enables the assessment of relationship between the pain and reactions that are generated in patient's eyes, bodily movements, and verbal expressions of discomfort, as well as degree of intensity of sensation of pain.⁵ Topical anesthesia gel/spray has been a gold standard in minimizing pain of oral injections. Herbal medicine is the mainstay of approximately 75- 80% of the world's population. This is mainly because herbal drugs have no side effects apart from being locally available and cost effective.² Sucrose also produces an analgesic effect. The sweet taste acts as a reward leaving a pleasant experience for the patient which is not the case while using the conventional topical anesthetic agents. Cold helps to overcome the feeling of discomfort after dental treatment with local anesthesia.² However, studies conducted by Kankkunen et al., and Ram et al. concluded that children after dental treatment with local anesthesia experienced pain relief by eating ice-cream and also reported a lower score of pain on the Wong-Baker Faces Pain Rating Scale.

Conclusion

According to this study it is concluded that using cryotherapy has low mean pain perception score followed by sweetening agent (Glucose) as compared to other Groups. It can be alternative to the conventional topical anesthesia agents in minimizing pain due to needle prick before administration of local anesthesia, as it is safe and effective. The sweet taste (Glucose) that acts as a reward and herbal agents can also be alternative to conventional topical anesthesia agents as they are easily available and cost effective.

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